

Mean-flow hydrodynamics for outflows in stellar evolution models

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Abstract

Mass loss is a crucial component in stellar evolution models, since it largely determines the rate of evolution at the later stages of a star's life. The dust-driven outflows from AGB stars are particularly important in this regard. Including AGB dust formation in a stellar evolution model does also require a model of these outflows. Since AGB stars exhibit large-amplitude pulsation, a model based on time-dependent radiation hydrodynamics (RHD) is needed in order to capture all the important physical aspects of dust formation. However, this cannot be afforded in a stellar evolution model. Here, a mean-flow model is presented, which include corrections to the steady-state model currently being used in AGB evolution models with dust formation.

1 Introduction

Asymptotic giant branch (AGB) stars have low effective temperatures, high and periodically varying luminosities and extended, often considerably dusty, circumstellar envelopes. The majority of these stars have also significant winds and some, especially the carbon-rich ones, are completely enshrouded with dust, which made radiation pressure on dust grains a natural assumption for the driving mechanism (Jura, 1986; Sedlmayr & Dominik, 1995; Habing & Olofsson, 2003). Dust-driven winds from AGB stars can now be regarded as a confirmed hypothesis, both from a theoretical and an observational point of view (Höfner, 2015).

A first attempt to include stellar dust production in stellar evolution modelling was made by Ferrarotti & Gail (2006). They combined a synthetic model of AGB evolution with a model of dust formation based on the method of moments (see, e.g., Gail & Sedlmayr, 1988) and a simple stationary wind model similar to that of Gail & Sedlmayr (1987), but without thermal gas pressure. It was later demonstrated by Ventura *et al.* (2012a,b) that this approach works also in combination with direct solution of the full set of stellar evolution equations and that previous theoretical dust yields of AGB stars were probably significantly overestimated. In fact, it seems now that the overall contribution of AGB stars to the cosmic dust budget is relatively small and that dust condensation in the interstellar medium may dominate the dust budget (see, e.g., Mattsson *et al.*, 2014) together with supernova produced dust.

Common practise in stellar evolution modelling has so far been to drop the gas-pressure term, neglect the effects of pulsation and use a prescription for mass-loss rate rather than calculating it within the framework of the model (Ferrarotti & Gail, 2006; Ventura *et al.*, 2012a,b; Nanni *et al.*, 2013, 2014). Neglecting the effects of pulsation and gas pressure is a good approximation as long as the ratio of radiative to gravitational acceleration $\Gamma \gg 1$, but will break down as $\Gamma \rightarrow 1$. A prescribed mass-loss rate enables modelling of dust formation as “post processing”, which is advantageous in the sense that existing grids of stellar evolution models do not need to be recomputed in order to explore dust formation on the AGB. However, this approach can be dangerous if the prescription is not reliable and, unfortunately, there is no truly reliable and general prescription. An attempt to improve upon this situation for carbon-rich AGB stars was made by Mattsson *et al.* (2010), which demonstrated the importance of treating the mass-loss rate as a function of the abundance of carbon available for dust formation and not just the fundamental stellar parameters such as luminosity and effective temperature. Grain sizes has also turned out to be an important parameter (Höfner, 2008; Mattsson & Höfner, 2011), which further complicates the picture.

It is quite clear, that the mass-loss rate as a function of fundamental stellar parameters and dust parameters such as grain size and the degree of dust condensation, cannot easily be reduced to a simple formula. AGB stars also exhibit large-amplitude pulsation, which requires a model based on time-dependent radiation hydrodynamics (RHD) in order to capture all the important physical aspects of dust formation and the development of a dust-driven wind. Combining such detailed wind modelling with stellar evolution modelling is computationally not feasible, however. Therefore, one has to either pre-compute large grids of wind models and use a look-up and interpolation routine to find the right mass-loss rate at a given time step in the stellar evolution sequence, or, find an acceptable way to model the mass-loss rate at low computational cost. The latter is the preferred alternative if the resultant mass-loss rate is accurate enough simply because it is closer to a self-consistent description and gives freedom to adjust wind-related input parameters.

In this paper, a mean-flow model of a dust-driven stellar wind is discussed, in which the net effect of the pulsation is taken into account in terms of an additional “wave pressure”.

2 Mean-flow theory

As stellar evolution models (and most AGB-star wind models) assume spherical symmetry, only the spherical-symmetry case will be considered, which makes the problem mathematically one-dimensional, since vanishing time derivatives will be assumed. A slow variation with time of the mean-flow quantities is of course still possible and a necessary adaption to the stellar evolution problem (the timescale of stellar evolution is much longer than that of the atmospheric dynamics). Finally, the expanding atmospheric gas is assumed to correspond to a highly compressible inviscid flow.

2.1 Favré averaging

In incompressible turbulence, so-called Reynolds decomposition (Reynolds, 1895) of pressure, temperature, velocity etc. is used to construct a mean-flow theory. In other words, a quantity Q_i is split into a mean \bar{q}_i and fluctuating part q'_i , where $\overline{q'_i} = 0$, but $\overline{q'_i q'_j} \neq 0$. Struck *et al.* (2004) used this approach to study the pulsation and wave dynamics of AGB stars, although it requires some further assumptions to be applicable to compressible flows.

A convenient way to handle short-term variations, which better suited for a compressible flow, is to use a mass-density weighted time average,

$$\tilde{q}_i \equiv \lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \int_{t_0}^{t_0+\tau} \rho Q_i dt \Big/ \int_{t_0}^{t_0+\tau} \rho dt = \frac{\overline{\rho Q_i}}{\bar{\rho}}, \quad (1)$$

which is known as the *Favré approximation*, where the decomposition is given by $Q_i = \tilde{q}_i + q''_i$ (Favré, 1969; Favre *et al.*, 1976). Then, $\overline{\rho q''_i} = 0$, while $\overline{q''_i} \neq 0$ and $\overline{\rho \tilde{q}_i} = \bar{\rho} \tilde{q}_i = \overline{\rho Q_i}$. The latter is equivalent to $\overline{q''_i} = \bar{q}_i - \tilde{q}_i$. The Favré approximation and its properties can also be understood in terms of a joint probability density function for ρ and Q_i which tends clarify many of the assumptions commonly made in mean-flow models of a compressible fluid (see Bilger, 1975).

Here, the principles outlined above will be applied to the basic conservation laws of a spherically symmetric fluid flow. More precisely, classical Reynolds decomposition is applied to pressure P and density ρ also for a fully compressible flow, i.e.,

$$P = \bar{P} + P', \quad \rho = \bar{\rho} + \rho', \quad (2)$$

with

$$\overline{P'} = 0, \quad \overline{\rho'} = 0, \quad (3)$$

while Favré averaging and corresponding decomposition is applied to the (radial) flow velocity u_r and the temperature T ,

$$u_r = \tilde{u}_r + u''_r, \quad T = \tilde{T} + T'', \quad (4)$$

with

$$\overline{\rho u''_r} = 0, \quad \overline{\rho T''} = 0, \quad \text{and} \quad \overline{u''_r} = \bar{u}_r - \tilde{u}_r \neq 0, \quad \overline{T''} = \bar{T} - \tilde{T} \neq 0. \quad (5)$$

For further details, see Canuto (1997).

2.2 Continuity equation

Mass conservation is obtained by requiring that the gas-mass density ρ satisfies the continuity equation (CE),

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (r^2 \rho u_r) = 0, \quad (6)$$

where u_r is the radial flow. Assuming a slowly varying mean (vanishing time derivatives), which is equivalent to “stationarity on average”, the Favré-averaged CE becomes

$$\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (r^2 \bar{\rho} \tilde{u}_r) = 0, \quad (7)$$

Thus, mass conservation implies $r^2 \bar{\rho} \tilde{u}_r = \text{constant}$, which in turn implies that the density structure can be obtained if \tilde{u}_r and the constant of integration are known.

2.3 Momentum equation (equation of motion)

The outflow of course needs to conserve momentum as well, which leads to an equation of motion (EOM). More precisely,

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho u_r) + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (r^2 \rho u_r^2) = -\frac{\partial P}{\partial r} - \rho f_r, \quad (8)$$

where u_r is the radial velocity component, P is the thermal gas pressure and ρf_r denotes an external force. Assuming stationarity on average and combining with the averaged CE above, the Favre-averaged EOM (in non-conservative form) simplifies to

$$\bar{\rho} \tilde{u}_r \frac{d\tilde{u}_r}{dr} = -\frac{d\bar{P}}{dr} + \overline{\rho f_r} - \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{d}{dr} \left[r^2 \overline{\rho (u''_r)^2} \right]. \quad (9)$$

Here, f_r is equal to the effective gravitational acceleration g_{eff} , which is the sum of the gravitational and radiative accelerations, i.e., $g_{\text{eff}} = g_{\text{grav}} + g_{\text{rad}}$. The effective acceleration can conveniently be approximated with

$$g_{\text{eff}} \approx (\Gamma - 1) \frac{GM_\star}{r^2}, \quad \Gamma \equiv \frac{\kappa_{\text{tot}} L_\star}{4\pi c GM_\star}, \quad (10)$$

where M_\star is the mass of the star, L_\star is the bolometric luminosity of the star, κ_{tot} is the total opacity of the gas (the sum of gas opacity and dust opacity) and c is the speed of light. Since $\rho g_{\text{eff}} = \bar{\rho} \tilde{g}_{\text{eff}}$, the averaged EOM will be of almost the same form as the usual stationary equation for radiatively driven stellar winds,

$$\tilde{u}_r \frac{d\tilde{u}_r}{dr} = -\frac{1}{\bar{\rho}} \frac{d\bar{P}}{dr} - \frac{GM_\star}{r^2} (1 - \tilde{\Gamma}) - \frac{1}{r^2 \bar{\rho}} \frac{d}{dr} \left[r^2 \overline{\rho (u_r'')^2} \right], \quad (11)$$

but with an extra term on the right-hand side, which is due to the pulsation and requires an additional closure relation.

2.4 Energy equation(s)

The total-energy equation (TEE), in conservative form, is written as

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho e_0) + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (r^2 \rho e_0 u_r) = \rho \dot{q} - \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (r^2 u_r P) - \rho f_r u_r, \quad e_0 = \frac{1}{2} u_r^2 + e \quad (12)$$

where e is the internal energy of the gas, i.e., $e = C_V T$ where C_V is the heat capacity and T the temperature of the gas, and the external force f_r is due to radiative and gravitational acceleration as described in the previous section. This equation can be split into a kinematic-energy ($\frac{1}{2} \rho u_r^2$) equation (KEE),

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{1}{2} \rho u_r^2 \right) + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\frac{1}{2} r^2 \bar{\rho} u_r^3 \right) = -\frac{u_r}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (r^2 P) - \rho f_r u_r, \quad (13)$$

and an internal-energy (ρe) equation (IEE),

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho e) + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (r^2 \rho e u_r) = \rho \dot{q} - \frac{P}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (r^2 u_r). \quad (14)$$

Because radiation processes dominate the cooling and heating of the gas, the rate of heat flux/transfer \dot{q} in a spherical atmosphere can be described by,

$$\dot{q} = 4\pi \int_0^\infty \kappa_{\text{gas}, \nu} (J_\nu - S_\nu) d\nu, \quad (15)$$

where $\kappa_{\text{gas}, \nu}$ is the gas opacity and S_ν is the source function of the gas. The case of radiative equilibrium, $\dot{q} = 0$, will be assumed for simplicity in what follows below.

Assuming stationarity on average, the Favré-averaged TEE is

$$\frac{d}{dr} \left[r^2 \left(\bar{\rho} \tilde{u}_r \tilde{e}_0 + \overline{\rho u_r'' e_0''} + \tilde{u}_r \bar{P} + \overline{u_r'' P} \right) \right] + r^2 \overline{\rho u_r f_r} = 0, \quad (16)$$

where

$$\bar{\rho} \tilde{e}_0 = \bar{\rho} \tilde{e} + \frac{1}{2} \bar{\rho} \tilde{u}_r^2 + \frac{1}{2} \overline{\rho (u_r'')^2}. \quad (17)$$

For an ideal gas, the equation of state (EOS) is

$$P = R \rho T, \quad (18)$$

where the gas constant R is the difference between the heat capacities C_V and C_P , i.e., $R = C_P - C_V$. Using this equation of state, and the fact that $e = C_V T$, it is straight forward to show that

$$\overline{u_r'' P} + \overline{\rho u_r'' e_0''} = C_V \overline{\rho u_r'' T} + \tilde{u}_r \overline{\rho (u_r'')^2} + \frac{1}{2} \overline{\rho (u_r'')^3}, \quad (19)$$

which inserted into Eq. (16) yields

$$\frac{d}{dr} \left\{ r^2 \left[\bar{\rho} \tilde{u}_r \tilde{e} + \frac{1}{2} \bar{\rho} \tilde{u}_r^3 + \frac{3}{2} \overline{\rho (u_r'')^2} \tilde{u}_r + \tilde{u}_r (C_P - C_V) \overline{\rho T} + C_V \overline{\rho u_r'' T} + \frac{1}{2} \overline{\rho (u_r'')^3} \right] \right\} + r^2 \overline{\rho u_r f_r} = 0. \quad (20)$$

In the mean-flow/field theory of incompressible turbulence it is often assumed that the turbulent energy is small compared to the enthalpy. In such case, the last term within the brackets in Eq. (20) may be regarded as negligible. For the wave energy of the pulsation the situation is slightly different, but the last term can be dropped anyway, because the shocks induced by pulsation are behaving like travelling waves, which are eventually damped out. This will be implicitly assumed in subsequent applications of the Favré averaged TEE in the present paper.

Table 1: Stellar parameters and average outflow quantities at the outer boundary of the two numerical simulations of a carbon-rich AGB star mentioned in the text.

	Model A	Model B
$M_\star [M_\odot]$	0.75	0.75
$\log(L_\star/L_\odot)$	3.85	3.85
$T_{\text{eff}} [\text{K}]$	2400	2400
$\log(\tilde{\epsilon}_c)$	-2.90	-3.80
$\Delta u_p [\text{km s}^{-1}]$	4.0	2.0
$\dot{M} [10^{-6} M_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1}]$	9.24	1.05
$u_{\text{out}} [\text{km s}^{-1}]$	42.1	1.64
$\Delta u_{\text{out}} [\text{km s}^{-1}]$	2.31	0.03
$\rho_d/\rho \cdot 10^3$	5.94	0.31
f_c	0.56	0.23
Γ	~ 5	~ 0.2

3 Gas pressure and temperature structure

The average thermal gas pressure makes a non-negligible contribution to the outflow of an AGB star. To obtain the gas pressure gradient without adding an energy equation (which should be avoided in stellar-evolution applications due to the computational expense), one has to either adopt a barotropic/polytropic equation of state (EOS) or a prescription for the mean temperature structure $\bar{T}(r)$.

3.1 Gas pressure

The gas pressure is obtained via an EOS, which for a neutral non-relativistic gas is usually the ideal gas law,

$$P = \frac{k_B}{\mu m_H} \rho T, \quad (21)$$

where k_B is the Boltzmann constant μ is the “mean molecular weight” of the gas and m_H is the mass of a hydrogen atom. To obtain the gas-pressure gradient occurring in the EOM, the temperature structure must be known. Thus, one has to solve the IEE and the full radiative transfer problem, which would be an inhibiting extension to a stellar evolution code.

For a polytropic EOS, on the other hand, where $P \propto \rho^{1+1/n}$, with n the “polytropic index”, the sound speed is $c_s^2 \propto \rho^{1/n}$. In combination with the averaged CE, the average gas-pressure acceleration can be estimated by

$$\frac{1}{\bar{\rho}} \frac{d\bar{P}}{dr} = -\bar{c}_s^2(r) \left(\frac{2}{r} + \frac{d \ln \bar{u}_r}{dr} \right), \quad (22)$$

which holds also for an isothermal EOS. This polytropic approximation works rather well for the wind region, which is evident from Fig. 1 in Mattsson (2016), showing the average gas-pressure profile for a RHD simulation of a slow wind escaping from a carbon-rich AGB star (an extension of a model from Mattsson *et al.*, 2010, see Model B in Table 1 for details). With a polytropic index $n = 2.5$ (the “standard value” for stellar structures) the agreement with the average profile outside the dust-formation zone ($r/R_\star \gtrsim 2$) is very good when the polytropic EOS has been “anchored” to the outer boundary. Calibration at the inner boundary can in the same way yield a good agreement to the profile inside $r/R_\star \gtrsim 2$. Adopting two different calibrations for the inner and the outer regions should provide a sufficiently accurate approximation. Note, also, that the polytropic approximation works equally well for the case of a strong wind (such as Model A in Table 1).

3.2 Temperature structure

Using the standard EOS for an ideal gas, one should preferably solve the IEE in order to obtain the temperature structure, as remarked above. However, for practical reason one may want to avoid this in a stellar-evolution setting and use an approximation of the temperature structure. A common choice for such an approximation is the *Lucy approximation* (see, e.g., Ferrarotti & Gail, 2006; Nanni *et al.*, 2013, 2014; Ventura *et al.*, 2012a,b). That is,

$$T_L^4(r) = T_{\text{eff}}^4 W(r) + \frac{3}{4} \frac{d\tau}{dr}, \quad W(r) = \frac{1}{2} \left[1 - \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{R_\star}{r} \right)^2} \right], \quad (23)$$

where R_* is the effective stellar radius and τ is the optical depth of the wind region. It has not been shown here, or elsewhere, that the temperature profile of the Lucy-approximation can be equated with the mass-weighted average \tilde{T} . But for the sake of simplicity, it will here be assumed that $\tilde{T} = T_L$. If $\tilde{T}(r)$ is known, albeit just approximately, then the gas-pressure acceleration (first term) in (11) can be obtained from

$$\frac{1}{\bar{\rho}} \frac{d\bar{P}}{dr} = \tilde{c}_s^2 \left(\frac{d \ln \tilde{T}}{dr} - \frac{2}{r} - \frac{d \ln \tilde{u}_r}{dr} \right), \quad \tilde{c}_s^2 = \frac{k_B}{\mu m_H} \tilde{T}, \quad (24)$$

where k_B , μ and m_H are as previously defined.

An approximation to the temperature structure is also implicitly contained in the polytropic approximation discussed above. Combination of eq. (21) and a polytropic EOS $P \propto \rho^{1+1/n}$ yields $T \propto \rho^{1/n}$. In stellar evolution applications, this relation should work as well as the Lucy approximation in approximating the temperature structure, which is needed to model the dust formation.

4 Pulsation and wave pressure

4.1 Piston boundary and the kinetic-energy injection by the pulsation

In numerical simulations the pulsation is modelled by a piston boundary condition, which generates the long-period light variation which is so characteristic for AGB stars. It also generates shockwaves which plays an important role in dust and wind formation (Mattsson *et al.*, 2008; Höfner, 2015; Liljegren *et al.*, 2016). The radial displacement of the ‘‘piston’’ is given by

$$r_{\text{in}}(t) = r_{\text{in}}(0) + 2\pi \mathcal{P} \Delta u_p \sin \left(\frac{2\pi t}{\mathcal{P}} \right), \quad (25)$$

where Δu_p is the piston (velocity) amplitude (typically a few km s⁻¹) and \mathcal{P} is the pulsation period. Consequently, there is a net input of kinetic energy, because

$$\overline{(u''_{\text{in}})^2} \approx \overline{(u'_{\text{in}})^2} = \frac{1}{2} \Delta u_p^2 > 0. \quad (26)$$

However, using Favré averaging, the average must be taken over the kinetic-energy density of the variations $\frac{1}{2}\rho(u'')^2$. But since the density variation at the inner boundary follows the displacement due to the pulsation, a convenient approximation can be introduced. Series expansion of ρ around $r = r_0$, where r_0 is the location of the inner boundary at $t = 0$, yields

$$\rho(r_{\text{in}}, t) \approx \rho(r_0, t) + (r - r_0) \left(\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial r} \right)_{r=r_0} + \dots, \quad (27)$$

which after averaging leads to $\overline{\rho_{\text{in}}(u''_{\text{in}})^2} \approx \frac{1}{2} \bar{\rho}_{\text{in}} \Delta u_p^2$, where $\bar{\rho}_{\text{in}} = \overline{\rho(r_0, t)}$.

4.2 Energy equation and wave pressure

The pulsation simulated by the piston boundary generates a continuous ‘‘train’’ of shockwaves, which leads to a so-called wave pressure. Estimating this wave pressure can be difficult since many processes can strengthen or dampen the shockwaves. Here, only simple estimates will be discussed, but the reader should bear in mind that more sophisticated models for the wave pressure can easily be obtained.

Assuming an isothermal EOS, i.e., a constant temperature T_0 and constant internal energy e , Eq. (20) reduces to

$$\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{d}{dr} \left\{ r^2 \left[\bar{\rho} \tilde{u}_r \tilde{e} + \frac{1}{2} \bar{\rho} \tilde{u}_r^3 + \frac{3}{2} \overline{\rho (u'_r)^2} \tilde{u}_r + \tilde{u}_r (C_P - C_V) \bar{\rho} T_0 \right] \right\} + \overline{\rho u_r f_r} = 0. \quad (28)$$

Since $r^2 \bar{\rho} \tilde{u}_r = \text{constant}$, the above equation can be further reduced to

$$\frac{d}{dr} \left\{ r^2 \left[\frac{1}{2} \bar{\rho} \tilde{u}_r^3 + \frac{3}{2} \overline{\rho (u'_r)^2} \tilde{u}_r \right] \right\} + r^2 \overline{\rho u_r f_r} = 0. \quad (29)$$

A reasonable approximation (or exact expression in case f_r is time-independent) for the forcing term is

$$r^2 \overline{\rho u_r f_r} \approx r^2 \bar{\rho} \tilde{u}_r \bar{f}_r = \frac{\dot{M}}{4\pi} \bar{f}_r, \quad (30)$$

where \dot{M} is the average mass-loss rate $\dot{M} = 4\pi r^2 \bar{\rho} \tilde{u}_r = \text{constant}$. Inserting Eq. (30) into Eq. (29) and dividing by $\dot{M}/4\pi$ gives

$$\tilde{u}_r \frac{d\tilde{u}_r}{dr} + \frac{3}{2 r^2 \bar{\rho} \tilde{u}_r} \frac{d}{dr} \left[r^2 \overline{\rho (u'_r)^2} \tilde{u}_r \right] + \bar{f}_r = 0. \quad (31)$$

Combining the equation above with the EOM, i.e., Eq. (11) with an isothermal EOS, results in

$$\frac{1}{r^2 \bar{\rho}} \frac{d}{dr} \left[r^2 \overline{\rho (u_r'')^2} \right] + \left[2 c_s^2 + 3 \frac{\overline{\rho (u_r'')^2}}{\bar{\rho}} \right] \frac{d \ln \tilde{u}_r}{dr} + \frac{4 c_s^2}{r} = 0, \quad (32)$$

which provides an expression for the wave-pressure term in Eq. (11).

The simplistic expression suggested in Mattsson (2016) involved some “cheating” in its derivation, in the sense that it was assumed that

$$\tilde{u}_r \frac{d \tilde{u}_r}{dr} + \bar{f}_r \approx 0, \quad (33)$$

which is a well-motivated approximation in the strong-wind regime where $\tilde{\Gamma} \gg 1$, but not otherwise. This is a somewhat shaky assumption since it implies that the wave-pressure and gas-pressure terms are always small relative to the radiation pressure, which they are sometimes not. However, despite the “cheating” in the derivation, it still provides a first-order approximation of the wave pressure in the outer parts of the atmosphere (the wind region) due to pulsation in the isothermal limit. However, with the approximation above, Eq. (29) reduces to a very simple expression,

$$\frac{d}{dr} \left[r^2 \overline{\rho (u_r'')^2} \tilde{u}_r \right] \approx 0. \quad (34)$$

Integrating this simple equation, making use of the linearised relation for the kinetic-energy injection by pulsation (see Section 4.1), yields

$$r^2 \overline{\rho (u_r'')^2} \tilde{u}_r \approx \frac{1}{2} r_{\text{in}}^2 \bar{\rho}_{\text{in}} \tilde{u}_{\text{in}} \Delta u_p^2. \quad (35)$$

Dividing by \tilde{u}_r and taking the derivative w.r.t. r results in an expression for the wave-pressure term in the EOM (11),

$$\frac{1}{r^2 \bar{\rho}} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left[r^2 \overline{\rho (u_r'')^2} \right] \approx -\frac{1}{2} \Delta u_p^2 \frac{d \ln \tilde{u}_r}{dr}, \quad (36)$$

which is a very convenient approximation as the right-hand side can be evaluated analytically and therefore allows exact solutions to the EOM for special cases, e.g., isothermal winds.

To improve the simplistic model above, one may consider the fact that $\tilde{u}_r \approx 0$ in the inner part of the atmosphere where $\tilde{\Gamma} \approx 0$. A reasonable assumption, which is consistent with $\tilde{u}_r \approx 0$ if $\tilde{\Gamma} \approx 0$, would be

$$\tilde{u}_r \frac{d \tilde{u}_r}{dr} - \frac{GM_\star}{r^2} \tilde{\Gamma} \approx 0, \quad (37)$$

which is the same as to assume that the gas pressure and gravity terms roughly cancel each other in the inner part and both become insignificant in the outer part of the extended atmosphere. This leads to an energy equation of the form

$$\frac{d}{dr} \left[r^2 \overline{\rho (u_r'')^2} \tilde{u}_r \right] + \frac{\dot{M}}{6 \pi} \frac{GM_\star}{r^2} \approx 0. \quad (38)$$

Following the same procedure as in the over-simplistic case, the wave-pressure term becomes

$$\frac{1}{r^2 \bar{\rho}} \frac{d}{dr} \left[r^2 \overline{\rho (u_r'')^2} \right] \approx -\frac{1}{3} \frac{u_{\text{esc}}^2}{r} - \left(\frac{1}{3} u_{\text{esc}}^2 + \frac{1}{2} \Delta u_p^2 \right) \frac{d \ln \tilde{u}_r}{dr}, \quad \text{where } u_{\text{esc}} = \sqrt{\frac{2GM_\star}{r}}. \quad (39)$$

The right-hand side of this equation cannot be evaluated analytically, but is easy to integrate numerically. Hence, inclusion of this approximation in a stellar evolution context is straight forward.

Another approximation, which has the advantage of being naturally parameterisable, is based upon the observation that $\overline{\rho (u_r'')^2} \approx \gamma \bar{\rho} \Delta u_p^2$, where γ is a parameter of order unity. A relation of this kind has been seen in numerical simulations of dust-driven winds from carbon-rich AGB stars (Mattsson *et al.*, 2008). That is, the density-weighted average of the velocity variations remains approximately constant with respect to r and is similar in magnitude to the piston amplitude Δu_p . Thus, a parametric relation of the form

$$\frac{1}{r^2 \bar{\rho}} \frac{d}{dr} \left[r^2 \overline{\rho (u_r'')^2} \right] + [2 c_s^2 + \gamma \Delta u_p^2] \frac{d \ln \tilde{u}_r}{dr} + \frac{4 c_s^2}{r} = 0, \quad (40)$$

may serve as a sufficiently flexible model. Carefully chosen values of γ and c_s should lead to an approximation of the wave-pressure term which is accurate enough. The isothermal condition, used in all approximations discussed above, can be relaxed by introducing a polytropic EOS in the derivation, but the wave-pressure terms given in Eqs. (39) and (40) is likely sufficient for stellar evolution modelling given the magnitude of uncertainty of fundamental stellar parameters on the AGB. Moreover, it can be shown that the isothermal condition is effectively local, i.e., the shocks formed due to the pulsation are isothermal while the overall atmospheric structure (including the wind region) is not.

5 Radiative acceleration

The radiative acceleration of the gas in an AGB atmosphere is mainly a consequence of the momentum transfer from radiation to dust grains. Thus, κ_{tot} can be replaced by the opacity κ_{d} due to dust grains in the atmospheric gas. In the Rayleigh limit ($\lambda \gg 2\pi a$), the dust opacity of the gas at wavelength λ becomes

$$\kappa_{\lambda} = \frac{\pi}{\rho} \int_0^{\infty} a^3 Q'_{\text{abs}}(\lambda) f(a) da, \quad (41)$$

where f is the number density of grains of radius a , $Q'_{\text{abs}}(\lambda) = Q_{\text{abs}}(a, \lambda)/a$, where Q_{abs} is the ratio of the effective to the geometric cross-section. Note, however, that for critical winds this assumption puts a bias on the quantitative result (see Mattsson & Höfner, 2011).

It is convenient to introduce an average dust opacity defined as

$$\langle \kappa_{\text{d}} \rangle = \frac{1}{L_{\star}} \int_0^{\infty} \kappa_{\lambda} L_{\star, \lambda} d\lambda, \quad (42)$$

where L_{\star} is the bolometric luminosity. Similarly, the average opacity of the *grain material* can (in the Rayleigh limit) be defined as

$$\langle \kappa_{\text{gr}} \rangle = \frac{3}{4 \rho_{\text{gr}} L_{\star}} \int_0^{\infty} Q'_{\text{abs}}(\lambda) L_{\star, \lambda} d\lambda, \quad (43)$$

where ρ_{gr} is the bulk density of the grain material. Combination of Eqs. (41), (42) and (43) leads to a simple scaling relation between dust-to-gas ratio and the ratio of the average material density to the average dust opacity of the gas, $\rho_{\text{d}}/\rho = \langle \kappa_{\text{d}} \rangle / \langle \kappa_{\text{gr}} \rangle$, which can be used to estimate the efficiency of radiative acceleration, provided that ρ_{d} is known,

$$\Gamma = \frac{\langle \kappa_{\text{d}} \rangle L_{\star}}{4\pi c G M_{\star}} = \frac{\langle \kappa_{\text{gr}} \rangle L_{\star}}{4\pi c G M_{\star}} \frac{\rho_{\text{d}}}{\rho}. \quad (44)$$

Favré averaging yields

$$\overline{\rho \Gamma} = \bar{\rho} \tilde{\Gamma} = \frac{\langle \kappa_{\text{gr}} \rangle \overline{L_{\star} \rho_{\text{d}}}}{4\pi c G M_{\star}}, \quad (45)$$

which reveals a potential problem: are ρ_{d} and L_{\star} statistically dependent or not? It is tempting to assume that they are statistically independent, so that $\overline{L_{\star} \rho_{\text{d}}} = \bar{L}_{\star} \bar{\rho}_{\text{d}}$, but the cyclic variation of the dust formation does not necessarily correlate at all with the fundamental mode of pulsation and the resultant luminosity variation. As recently shown by Liljegren *et al.* (2016), the degree of correlation between ρ_{d} (or actually κ_{d}) and L_{\star} can be decisive for whether a dust-driven wind will develop or not. Suppose $\rho_{\text{d}} = \bar{\rho}_{\text{d}} + \rho'_{\text{d}}$ and $L_{\star} = \bar{L}_{\star} + L'_{\star}$. Then

$$\overline{\rho \Gamma} \propto \overline{L_{\star} \rho_{\text{d}}} = \bar{L}_{\star} \bar{\rho}_{\text{d}} + \overline{L'_{\star} \rho'_{\text{d}}}, \quad (46)$$

where the last term on the right-hand side can make a positive contribution in the wind-acceleration zone improving the conditions for wind formation. An *anti-correlation* between ρ_{d} and L_{\star} will, on the other hand, lead to a negative contribution from $\overline{L'_{\star} \rho'_{\text{d}}}$. Thus, in a stellar evolution context, it is probably fair to assume that $\overline{L'_{\star} \rho'_{\text{d}}} \approx 0$ on average¹.

If the radiative acceleration is large (formally, if $\Gamma \gg 1$), the thermal gas pressure and pulsation of the star does not add significantly to the kinetic energy of the wind. Such winds are clearly *dust-driven winds*. The expected development of shocks which do not quickly dissipate (see Fig. 1, left panel), implies that the root-mean-square of the fluctuations have a relatively weak radial gradient. An approximate EOM is therefore

$$4\pi \frac{d}{dr} (r^2 \bar{\rho} \tilde{u}_r^2) \approx \frac{\rho \langle \kappa_{\text{d}} \rangle L_{\star}}{c} = \langle \kappa_{\text{gr}} \rangle \frac{\rho_{\text{d}} L_{\star}}{c}. \quad (47)$$

Integrating and assuming $\overline{L'_{\star} \rho'_{\text{d}}} \approx 0$, one arrives at $4\pi r^2 \bar{\rho} \tilde{u}_r^2 \approx \bar{\tau}_{\text{w}} \bar{L}_{\star} / c$, where the average optical depth of the wind region is given by

$$\bar{\tau}_{\text{w}} = \int_{r_{\text{in}}}^r \overline{\rho \langle \kappa_{\text{d}} \rangle} dx = \langle \kappa_{\text{gr}} \rangle \int_{r_{\text{in}}}^r \bar{\rho}_{\text{d}} dx. \quad (48)$$

Thus, when $\Gamma \gg 1$, the velocity profile of the outflow is well approximated by

$$\tilde{u}_r^2(r) \approx \frac{\bar{\tau}_{\text{w}}(r) \bar{L}_{\star}}{4\pi c r^2 \bar{\rho}(r)} \leftrightarrow \tilde{u}_r(r) \approx \frac{\bar{\tau}_{\text{w}}(r) \bar{L}_{\star}}{c \dot{M}}, \quad (49)$$

which is essentially identical to a well-known result for stationary winds (see Lamers & Cassinelli, 1999) and defines the character of a strongly dust-driven outflow. Note that this approximation works also for a moderately large Γ , but may in such case require some re-scaling to precisely match the wind profile (see Fig. 1).

¹Near the inner boundary, ρ and L_{\star} are obviously correlated. Thus, $\overline{L'_{\star} \rho'_{\text{d}}} \approx 0$ cannot hold throughout the whole atmosphere.

Figure 1: Left: average wind profile of a strong-wind simulation (Model A) compared to the analytical prediction by eq.(49) using averaged quantities. Right: same as left panel, but for a slow critical-wind simulation (Model B). The shaded areas shows the 1σ -deviation from the mean of the simulated flows.

6 Summary and examples

6.1 Resultant equations

Here follows a summary of the equations derived so far. Assuming mean-flow conditions and applying Favré averaging to the Euler equations adapted for a dust-driven stellar wind from an AGB star leads to a CE of the form

$$\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (r^2 \bar{\rho} \tilde{u}_r) = 0, \quad (50)$$

and an EOM of the form

$$\tilde{u}_r \frac{d\tilde{u}_r}{dr} = -\frac{1}{\bar{\rho}} \frac{d\bar{P}}{dr} - \frac{GM_\star}{r^2} (1 - \tilde{\Gamma}) + f_{\text{wp}}, \quad (51)$$

where the last term (wave pressure due to the pulsation) may, for instance, be the isothermal approximation suggested in Section 4.1, i.e.,

$$f_{\text{wp}} = \left[2c_{s,0}^2 + 3 \frac{\rho (u_r'')^2}{\bar{\rho}} \right] \frac{d \ln \tilde{u}_r}{dr} + \frac{4c_{s,0}^2}{r}. \quad (52)$$

The gas-pressure gradient in case of a polytropic EOS is

$$\frac{d\bar{P}}{dr} = -\bar{\rho} c_s^2 \left(\frac{2}{r} + \frac{d \ln \tilde{u}_r}{dr} \right), \quad c_s^2 = \frac{n+1}{n} \frac{P_0}{\rho_0} \left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_0} \right)^{1/n}, \quad (53)$$

and the temperature gradient becomes

$$\frac{d\tilde{T}}{dr} = \left(\tilde{T} - \frac{\mu m_{\text{H}} c_s^2}{k_{\text{B}}} \right) \left(\frac{2}{r} + \frac{d \ln \tilde{u}_r}{dr} \right). \quad (54)$$

Alternatively, one may use the temperature structure obtained from the Lucy approximation (see Eq. 23) and combine with the regular EOS for an ideal gas to obtain the pressure gradient. In either case, with appropriate boundary conditions in combination with a model of dust formation and dust opacity (to obtain $\tilde{\Gamma}$), one has a closed system of equations, which for can provide mass-loss rate, wind velocity and other relevant parameters without any additional assumptions (note that wind models currently used in stellar evolution modelling are usually based on some prescription of the mass-loss rate, see, e.g., Ferrarotti & Gail, 2006; Ventura *et al.*, 2012a,b; Nanni *et al.*, 2013, 2014).

6.2 Boundary and auxiliary conditions

A few basic conditions must be fulfilled in order to obtain a physically consistent and meaningful solution to the EOM (Eq. 51). The EOM can be written on a form similar to the Parker (1958) wind equation,

$$\left(\frac{\tilde{u}_r^2}{c_s^2} - 1\right) \frac{d \ln \tilde{u}_r}{dr} = \frac{2}{r} - \frac{GM_\star}{c_s^2 r^2} (1 - \tilde{\Gamma}) + \frac{f_{\text{WP}}}{c_s^2}, \quad (55)$$

where the sonic radius r_s , i.e., where $\tilde{u}_r = c_s$ is located closer to the centre of the star than the condensation radius r_c , where dust condensation becomes efficient and $\tilde{\Gamma} > 0$. At $r = r_s$, the right-hand side of Eq. (55) becomes zero, which suggests that, on average, the gas and wave pressure is in balance with the gravitational pull since $\tilde{\Gamma} \approx 0$. That the right-hand side vanishes may, in fact, be assumed as an auxiliary condition inside $r = r_c$ (Gail & Sedlmayr, 1986). Then,

$$\frac{2c_s^2}{r} - \frac{GM_\star}{r^2} + f_{\text{WP}} = 0, \quad r \leq r_c, \quad (56)$$

$$\left(\frac{\tilde{u}_r^2}{c_s^2} - 1\right) \frac{d \ln \tilde{u}_r}{dr} = \frac{2}{r} - \frac{GM_\star}{c_s^2 r^2} (1 - \tilde{\Gamma}) + \frac{f_{\text{WP}}}{c_s^2}, \quad r > r_c, \quad (57)$$

where all quantities are as previously defined. The inner boundary for the wind model can be the condensation radius, since one may assume there is no net flow inside this radius. In such case, at $r_{\text{in}} = r_c$, it is more or less necessary to adopt the following inner-boundary conditions:

$$\tilde{u}_r = 0, \quad \frac{d\tilde{u}_r}{dr} = 0, \quad (58)$$

which acts as a regularisation condition for any numerical treatment of the problem.

6.3 Isothermal toy model

Adopting the somewhat oversimplified wave-pressure model suggested by Mattsson (2016, see also Eq. 36 in the present paper), an isothermal EOS and introducing the dimensionless variables,

$$\mathcal{U} = \frac{\tilde{u}_r}{\alpha}, \quad \mathcal{R} = \frac{r}{r_\alpha}, \quad r_\alpha = \frac{GM_\star}{2\alpha^2}, \quad (59)$$

one may write the EOM in the form

$$(\mathcal{U}^2 - 1) \frac{d \ln \mathcal{U}}{d \mathcal{R}} = \frac{2}{\mathcal{R}} \left(\frac{c_s}{\alpha}\right)^2 - \frac{2}{\mathcal{R}^2} (1 - \tilde{\Gamma}), \quad (60)$$

where α and c_s are constants. The acceleration ratio $\tilde{\Gamma}$ is normally a function temperature, primarily, which is why an isothermal model would imply an essentially constant ratio $\tilde{\Gamma} = \Gamma_0$. Here, it will be assumed that $\tilde{\Gamma} = 0$ for $r < r_c$ and $\tilde{\Gamma} = \Gamma_0$ for $r \geq r_c$.

The wind equation derived above can be solved analytically in terms of the Lambert W function, which can be defined as the solution to the equation $z = W(z) e^{W(z)}$ (Corless *et al.*, 1996). Integrating eq. (61) from $\mathcal{R} = 1$ to some arbitrary radius $\mathcal{R} = \mathcal{R}'$ one obtains an implicit transcendental equation for \mathcal{U} as a function of \mathcal{R} (Cranmer, 2004),

$$\mathcal{U}^2 - \ln(\mathcal{U}^2) - 1 = 4 \left(\frac{c_s}{\alpha}\right)^2 \ln(\mathcal{R}') + 4 \left(\frac{1}{\mathcal{R}'} - 1\right) (1 - \tilde{\Gamma}). \quad (61)$$

By definition $\mathcal{U} = 1$ when $\mathcal{R} = 1$. One may assume that $r_\alpha < r_c$ and $\tilde{\Gamma} > 0$. At $r = r_\alpha$ ($\mathcal{R} = 1$) one would then have $\tilde{\Gamma} = 0$. In Fig. 2, solutions to (61) for the case $\log(L_\star/L_\odot) = 3.85$, $M_\star = 1 M_\odot$ and an isothermal ($c_s = 2.0 \text{ km s}^{-1}$) wind region beyond the movable singularity (which coincides with the sonic point if $\Delta u_p = 0$) at

$$r_c = \frac{GM_\star}{2\alpha^2}, \quad \alpha^2 = c_s^2 + \frac{1}{2}\alpha^2, \quad (62)$$

are shown in physical units as illustrative examples. Clearly, outflows can be sustained even if $\tilde{\Gamma} < 1$ and for small and moderate values of $\tilde{\Gamma}$ (in the left panel of Fig. 2 the acceleration ratio $\tilde{\Gamma} = 1.6$), the thermal gas pressure and the pulsation amplitude Δu_p have non-negligible effects on the wind acceleration in this simplified mean-flow model. This has also been observed in numerical models (Mattsson *et al.*, 2007)

As shown in Section 5, the dust-to-gas ratio is approximately equal to the ratio of the average material density (κ_{gr}) to the average dust opacity of the gas, i.e., $\rho_d/\rho = \langle \kappa_d \rangle / \langle \kappa_{\text{gr}} \rangle$. Thus, for a given outflow velocity u_r , at a given radius r ,

$$\frac{\bar{\rho}_{d,\alpha}}{\bar{\rho}_d} \approx 1 - \left(\frac{\tilde{\Gamma} - 1}{\tilde{\Gamma}}\right) \frac{\ln(\omega) - 4c_s^2/\alpha^2 \ln(r/r_c)}{\omega - 1}, \quad \omega = \left(\frac{u_r}{\alpha}\right)^2, \quad (63)$$

Figure 2: Wind profiles for the isothermal toy model with different Γ values (left) and values of the piston velocity amplitude (right). All profiles correspond to $\log(L_*/L_\odot) = 3.85$ and $M_* = 1 M_\odot$.

where $\bar{\rho}_{d,\alpha}$ is the dust density with gas and pulsation pressure included and $\tilde{\Gamma}$ is the radiative acceleration ratio needed in case of only radiation pressure. Fig. 3 shows, for $c_s = 2.0 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, $r/r_c = 10$, the $\bar{\rho}_{d,\alpha}$ required to obtain a given u_r with the two new pressure terms included. The required dust density is significantly smaller for slow winds, compared to the case with only radiation pressure, which has important implications (e.g., lower dust yields).

6.4 Effects on AGB dust yields

Simple AGB-wind models, such as those used to include AGB-star dust formation in stellar evolution modelling (Ventura *et al.*, 2012a,b; Nanni *et al.*, 2013, 2014), often neglect the effects of gas pressure as well as “wave pressure”, which may put a bias on the efficiency of dust production. Since $\Gamma \propto \kappa_d \propto \rho_d/\rho$ (see Section 5), requiring that $\Gamma > 1$ forces the dust-to-gas ratio to be above a certain value, because there is a continuous mass loss on the AGB due to all common mass-loss prescriptions (e.g., Bloeker, 1995). The dust yield, i.e., the total mass of dust lost from the star during the AGB, will thus be lower if the dust-to-gas ratio is generally lower, as argued by Mattsson *et al.* (2015).

In view of the results obtained with the isothermal toy model described above, the need for dust to sustain a wind is obviously smaller the larger the parameter α is. Defining the *dust-loss rate* and *total dust yield* as

$$\dot{M}_d \equiv \frac{\bar{\rho}_d}{\bar{\rho}} \dot{M} = 4\pi r^2 \bar{\rho}_d u_r, \quad y_d \equiv \int_{\tau_{\text{AGB}}} \dot{M}_d(t) dt \quad (64)$$

it is clear that if a lower dust density ρ_d is sufficient to reach a certain mass-loss rate, also the total dust yield y_d will be less.

Imposing a certain mass-loss rate and requiring that the outflow should be dust-driven, will essentially make the efficiency of dust formation an input parameter and not a result of the modelling. The dust yield is an integral quantity, and can vary a lot depending on how, e.g., the mass-loss rate and the degree of dust condensation evolve. Moreover, the average *grain size* is sometimes decisive for whether a dust-driven outflow develops or not in some cases (Höfner, 2008; Mattsson & Höfner, 2011). Hence, stellar evolution models need a physically consistent treatment of mass loss. When calculating dust yields, it is important that dust formation efficiency leads to a certain mass-loss rate and not the other way around. Models of carbon-rich AGB stars suggest that dust may form without leading to dust-driven outflows (Mattsson *et al.*, 2015), which means the amount of dust expelled by the star can be insignificant despite ongoing dust formation. Outflows can, on the other hand, also be sustained if $\Gamma < 1$ (as shown in the present paper), which would also push the dust yields to lower values.

7 Conclusions and future work

A mean-flow model of a dust-driven stellar wind has been presented, in which the net effect of the pulsation is taken into account in terms of an additional “wave pressure”. The result is a set of equations which include corrections to the steady-state model currently being used in AGB evolution models with dust formation. Using these equations it is easily understood that slow winds will have $\Gamma < 1$ and that the dust yield obtained from stellar evolution modelling may be reduced. The reason for this is that the combination of thermal gas pressure and “pulsation pressure” is sometimes (slow winds in particular) making significant contributions to the maintenance of a wind.

The suggested mean-flow model also opens up for stellar evolution modelling where the mass-loss rate is directly computed and do not have to be prescribed by simplistic formulae. Implementing this will bring stellar evolution models a significant

Figure 3: The mean dust density for flows which include thermal gas pressure and pulsation (wave) pressure ($\rho_{d,\alpha}$) compared to flows without (ρ_d). This ratio can be reduced considerably for slow wind (low mass-loss rates).

step closer to self-consistency. More can of course be done to relax some of the approximations used in the present paper, but even a simplistic model, which include not only radiation pressure but also the effects from thermal gas pressure and shocks waves, will likely have non-negligible effects on the theoretical dust yields of AGB stars and improve quality of the calculations in general. One disadvantage of not using a prescribed mass-loss rate is that dust formation (yields) cannot be calculated as “post processing” of pre-existing stellar evolution tracks. But the advantages of having a more self-consistent model should outweigh this computational drawback.

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